

COOKSTOVE USABILITY PROTOCOL TEST SECTIONS

Test Section Name	Test Methods	Purpose
1 <i>Cookstove Characteristics Evaluation</i>	Quantitative measurements and observations	To measure stove dimensions and features.
2 <i>User Cooking Event Evaluation</i>	Quantitative measurements and observations	To measure fuel use, cooking event duration, and cooking practices and patterns during cooking activity.
3 <i>User Survey</i>	Quantified survey with primarily Likert-scale questions	To elicit perceptions about, and the relative importance of, each criterion from the cook's perspective.
4 <i>Semi-Structured Interview</i>	Qualitative interview	To clarify results from other test sections, as well as give participants the opportunity to share additional information they feel is important.